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Trump's order on US drug prices: President Trump signed an executive order aiming to reduce prescription drug prices by 30% to 80%. This order broadens [the previous Most Favoured Nation \(MFN\) rule applied to Medicare B](#) to also apply to Medicare D. It also aims to promote direct-to-consumer sales and drug importation from countries with lower prices. Experts question whether the order will achieve its goals due to a lack of details and potential legal challenges. Neither [pharma Companies](#) nor pharma critics such as Senator Bernie Sanders support the initiative.

Listing Date of Patents is Appropriate date for applying PM(NOC) Regulations: The Federal Court of Canada recently addressed the issue of the appropriate date to consider for patents listed under PM(NOC) Regulations. In [Bayer Inc v Amgen Canada Inc](#) and [Serono v Canada \(Health\)](#), the Courts confirmed that the critical date is the date that a patent is listed on the Patent Register by the Minister, not the date it was submitted for listing. This provides clarification to generic manufacturers and limits retroactive listings.

Lilly plans to expand Purdue University collaboration: Eli Lilly and Purdue University announced an extension of the Lilly-Purdue 360 Innovation program with a \$250 million investment over 8 years. Their partnership aims to accelerate Lilly's pharmaceutical innovation pipeline by integrating AI into drug discovery, developing the workforce, enhancing manufacturing processes, and bridging fundamental research and clinical applications.

Accelerating drug discovery with a single carbon atom: [Recent research](#) from the University of Oklahoma developed a new technique capable of accelerating drug discovery. This method, called skeletal editing, uses sulfenylcarbene as a metal-free reagent to insert a single carbon atom into heterocycles to effectively modify existing drugs into new ones during late-stage development. Compared to older methods, their process has a 98% yield effectiveness and is more environmentally friendly by using a softer reagent. This could minimize the steps required to optimize drugs and reduce the pharmaceutical development cost.